

The Study of General Aptitude in 10th class students according their Interest in Vidarbha Region

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Abstract- The aim was to explore the common aptitudes and interests of students from rural and urban areas of Vidarbha and match them with relevant courses in the five professional fields of medicine, engineering, commerce, arts, and applied arts. In this context, general aptitude tests and aptitude finder tests were utilized to identify the general aptitude and specific aptitudes of rural students. The researchers endeavored to integrate curricula related to the fields of medicine, engineering, commerce, arts, and applied arts. The Purpose of the present research study is recognized that if rural students were provided with proper educational and economic opportunities, they could progress in the right direction, achieve future success, and lead happy lives. The research revealed that while students in urban areas had access to educational, economic, social, physical, and natural facilities, their counterparts in rural areas lacked such access for the present research; data was collected using survey research method. The present research study covered nine out of eleven districts in Vidarbha region by purposive sampling method Furthermore, due to the inclusion of class 10 students in all Marathi medium schools across rural and urban areas of Vidarbha, the findings of the research were applicable to Class 10 students in Marathi medium schools throughout Vidarbha region. It was decided to get a certified standard from the office of "Departmental Business Guidance Centre, Nagpur" to analyze the collected information. After ensuring that the collected information was properly analyzed; the collected information was classified and analyzed as per the standard criteria. The finding of the research study is Interest and General aptitude in the field of medical and engineering of rural students is less as compared to urban students. However, the situation in the field of commerce and art is opposite. General aptitude and aptitude in the field of applied arts is also higher among urban students than rural students.

Keywords:-General aptitude test battery, Interest inventory test, Counselors, Teachers, Vidarbha region. General Aptitude, Interest

I. Introduction and Scope

The research demonstrated that students in rural areas possessed intrinsic qualities that required proper direction, facilities, and opportunities. In this regard, the research proved beneficial not only for the students but also for their teachers and parents.

Generally, after the result of the school examination, the students choose their field of further education or further professional course on the basis of the marks obtained in the school examination. In the age group of 14-16 years, every student is faced with the question, which course to choose next? Often, students choose their future courses on the advice of their friends or on the advice of their parents.

Sometimes it is the parents who try to impose their unfulfilled ambitions on the students. So choosing a burdensome course in future costs time and money. Finally comes the turn of repentance. Also choosing an easy course leads to dissatisfaction.

Students can be successful in their future life if they know their general aptitude and choose courses according to their interests.

Every student as well as their parents has some ambition for their child's future. They get a deep sense of what professional course they need and like according to their general aptitude. Every student has inherent qualities; if students choose their future course accordingly by finding those qualities then they can complete their future course with more interest in it.

Parents should help students choose courses in their field of interest. If the general aptitude and interests of the students are properly coordinated, they can be successful in their life.

The major need of the present time is to get proper guidance and counseling to the students and their parents. Today human life is very dynamic and changing rapidly. Educational guidance has become our essential need. If a student chooses a future course based on things like father's insistence, self-conception, school coercion, teacher's coercion and friends' ill-advise... he has to bear the consequences throughout his life.

Research Objective:-

To Comparative study of general aptitude and interests of urban and rural school students in Vidarbha region.

II. Literature Review

While reviewing the prior research, it is observed that the instruments used in the present research are completely different. Institute of Vocational Guidance and Selection, Mumbai has adapted the US test to Indian test in the presented research. For this, many business guides and counselors as well as psychologists have also helped. The tools used in the present research are completely different from the tools used by other researchers.

A. Bhattacharya (Chatterjee), S. L. Intodia, J. P. S. Tomar, S. Sharma, Mary John, h. Bhatnagar,

R.R. Joshi, D. D. Dabir, K. K. Jain, P. H. Mehta et al have researched and submitted their reports for Ph.D. in Education.

Most researchers have used the Bansal Occupational Interest Record (1975), Booker Mehendi Test of Verbal Creative Thinking (1973), Raven's Standard Progressive Matrices (1956), Kulshrestha Socio-Economic Status Scale (1975), Mathur and Chandel Parental Expression Scale (1975), English Uses Test, Depression Aptitude Test Battery (Cattell), Achievement Motivation Test (Prayag, Mehta), Occupational Aspiration Scale (Grewal), Interest Test Battery, Miller and Hallerus Occupational Aspiration Scale, Tools like English Language Ability Test, Comprehensive Course Tests etc. have been adopted. However, in the present research, General Aptitude Test Battery and Five Field Interest Inventory (Five Field Interest Inventory) at Vocational Guidance and Selection Institute, Mumbai. Two standard tests are adopted. And this is the most important distinction of the present research.

In the present research, there are eleven subtests in a general aptitude set, nine of which are used to detect nine general aptitudes in students. Also, five professional interest namely medical, engineering, arts, commerce and applied arts are explored through the "Five Fields Interest Inventory Test"

In the present research, only private secondary schools in rural and urban areas have been considered. Therefore, it can be seen that the present research is different from the previous research in many respects due to the differences in other research and the present research.

III. Methodology

For the present research, data was collected using survey research method. In this survey research method 'Survey Test ' was adopted. What subjects are students interested in? Or which factors have general validity? To check this, a measurement tool called 'Survey Test' has been adopted.

Sample Selection:-

Schools from all urban and rural areas of Vidarbha were selected by 'Purposive Sampling Method'. First of all, the number of students in class 10 in all Marathi medium schools in the urban division which are included in the present research was determined. In terms of sample, the knowledge of the presented research is more than that of other researchers. It has considered 9 districts out of total 11 districts of entire Vidarbha. It compares rural and urban students and draws conclusions. Such conclusions do not appear to have been drawn in prior research. Although other studies have considered urban and rural areas, there are also differences in terms of sample selection methods, comparison of rural and urban areas, comparison of boys and girls, geographical area, schools, etc.

IV. Tools of the study

The following tool has been selected as research tools to collect the information required in the present research.

- 1) General Aptitude Test Battery (GATB)
- 2) Interest Inventory Test (IIT)
- 1) General Aptitude Test Battery (GATB)

This test is standardized and evaluates the students in detail. The standards of this test are drawn. Its reliability is also complete.

At the same time accuracy and fairness are absolute. What are the common characteristics between rural and urban students? It gives valid information about how these skills can be used in future life. This test has come to our country from America.

It was prepared as follows according to the business elements required for business in America.

V. USGATB (United States GATB)

Part 1- Name Comparison- NC Part 2 - Computation - Comp.
Part 3- Three Dimensional Space-TDS Part 4- Vocabulary (English)
Part 5- Tool Matching-TM Part 6- Arithmetic Reason-AR Part 7- Form Matching -FM
Part 8- Mark Making - MM Part 9- Place (Performance) - P Part 10- Turn (Performance)
-T
Part 11- Assemble (Performance) -A Part 12- Dissemble (Performance) - D
The above US test was reflected in the Indian test from the Indian point of view by the
"Business Guidance and Selection Institute", a government body in Mumbai. That test
is as follows

VI. IVGS – GATB

Part 1- Name Comparison - NC
Part 2 - Arithmetic Computation- AC (English, Marathi) Part 3- Three Dimensional
Space-TDS
Part 4- Vocabulary in English- VE Part 5- Tool Matching -TM
Part 6- Arithmetic Reasoning- AR (English, Marathi) Part 7- Form Matching- FM
Part 8- Non Verbal Reason-NVR
Part 9- Vocabulary on Marathi/ Gujarati-VM/VG Part 10- Manual Dexterity - MD
Part 11- Mark Making -MM Part 12- Figure Dexterity - FD

In the present research a general aptitude test set was selected from the office of
"Departmental Vocational Guidance and Selection Institute, Nagpur". Out of the above
12 subtests, only 9 subtests have been used in the present research. The following are
the 9 sub-tests out of which.

1. Name Comparison- NC
2. Arithmetic Computation – AC
3. Three Dimensional Space-TDS
4. Vocabulary in English – VE
5. Tool Matching – TM
6. Arithmetic Reasoning-AR
7. Form Matching – FM
8. Non Verbal Reasoning – NVR
9. Vocabulary in Marathi-VM

VII. Interest Inventory Test:

Interest Inventory Test has been used in the present research. A person's aptitude is
measured by taking into account their interest in various occupations through the
aptitude finder test. Sorting and scoring of answers is done in such a way that marks
are obtained for different subjects. This score is defined with the help of standards.
Accordingly high and low tastes are drawn. In the present research, this new method is
adopted to understand our interest, choice and mental inclination.

In the present research, this new method is adopted to understand our interest, choice and mental inclination. There are five fields in this profession field aptitude finder test namely Medical, Engineering, Commerce, Arts and Applied Arts. In the Aptitude Finder Test Questionnaire, each question has to be answered in three ways: Yes, No and Don't Know.

Medical – VE/8, AR/8, NVR/6 Engineering – TDS/6, AR/4, NVR/5 Commerce - NC/6, VE/5, AR/4, VM/5 Art –VE/8, AR/4, FM/5, NVR/4, VM/8

Applied Arts- TDS/6, VE/5, AR/4, NVR/5

Deals with professions related to five fields namely medicine, engineering, commerce, arts and applied arts.

VIII. Procedure

First of all, the number of students in class 10 in all Marathi medium schools in the urban division which are included in the present research was determined.

The school in the urban division where the research went, with the help of the school's business guide and counselor, two to three groups of class 10th of the Marathi medium school was divided each time. A group consisted of 15 to 20 students. Each group was given a „General Aptitude Test Battery Set“ to solve. Immediately after leaving the test, the 'Five Field Interest Inventory Test' was also allowed to be solved after a period of five minutes. In the same way, the students of the rural section were tested like the students of the urban section.

IX. Result and Discussion

The difference observed in the general aptitude of rural and urban students in different types of professional fields does not seem to be much. The most observed variation in general aptitude 2.5% belongs to commerce sector. In other areas it is less.

In terms of Interest the largest difference observed between the Interest of rural and urban students is related to the field of commerce. The difference in other sectors is generally 2% is around While moving towards twenty first century it has become imperative to think about educational progress. The ever-increasing population and the problems arising from it, is a challenging issue facing the education sector. With the huge influx of students from schools and colleges and the attraction towards professions, choosing the right person for the right profession has become a very difficult task. In such a situation, it has become imperative to consider various career guidance services at the school level.

Today, with at least one new profession emerging at such a fast pace, the choice of profession has become a big question mark for the students who pass class 10th or 12th. In fact, it is very necessary to get the help of parents in such cases, but even at that level, we do not see a very happy picture in front of our eyes. Ignorance and professional

attitude of parents in general class on one side and high expectations of some parents on their children on the other, pressure on students, is a matter of concern.

In such cases only one ray of hope can be seen, and that is the various psychological tests administered at the school level. Two psychological tests, General Aptitude Test Set and Five Area Aptitude Test, are used in the present research.

In the present research, a different attempt has been made to find out the interests of school students by measuring their general aptitude. Out of total 11 districts of entire Vidarbha, nine districts have been considered. It compares rural and urban students and draws conclusions.

General aptitude and aptitude in the field of medical and engineering of rural students is less as compared to urban students. However, the situation in the field of commerce and art is opposite. General aptitude and aptitude in the field of applied arts is also higher among urban students than rural students.

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Table No.1
 Student's General Aptitude and Interest (Rural and Urban)

Sr. No.	Professional Field	General Aptitude		difference	Interest		Difference
		Rural	Urban		Rural	Urban	
1	Medical	75 (11.36%)	85 (12.97%)	10 (1.61%)	102 (15.45%)	116 (17.70%)	14 (2.25%)
2	Engineering	85 (12.87%)	96 (14.65%)	11 (1.78%)	110 (16.66%)	125 (19.08%)	15 (2.42%)
3	Commerce	216 (32.72%)	198 (30.22%)	08 (2.5%)	188 (28.48%)	160 (24.42%)	28 (4.06%)
4	Art	226 (34.24%)	216 (32.97%)	10 (1.27%)	179 (27.12%)	152 (24.20%)	27 (2.92%)
5	Applied Art	30 (4.54%)	35 (5.34%)	05 (0.80%)	46 (6.96%)	58 (8.85%)	12 (1.89%)
6	Other Fields	28 (4.24%)	25 (3.81%)	03 (0.43%)	35 (5.30%)	58 (6.71%)	09 (1.41%)
7	Total	660 (99.97%)	655 (99.96%)		660 (99.97%)	655 (99.96%)	

In this way, in the present research, the professional interest of the students was found out in five professional field's namely medical sector, engineering sector, commerce sector, arts sector and applied arts sector. Collected the necessary information and analyzed that information.

Table No. 2 Standard Based performance
 (9 Point Scale)

Standard	Performance
1	V. very Low Average
2	Very Low Average
3	Low Average
4	Below Average
5	Average
6	Above Average
7	High Average
8	Above High Average
9	Very High Average

It was decided to get a certified standard from the office of "Departmental Business Guidance Centre, Nagpur" to analyze the collected information. After ensuring that the collected information was properly analyzed, the collected information was classified and analyzed as per the standard criteria.

X. Conclusions

1. The General Aptitude of Medical field students in Rural Area is 11.36% and urban area is 12.97% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 1.61%.
2. The General Aptitude of Engineering students in Rural Area is 12.87% and urban area is 14.65% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 1.78%.
3. The General Aptitude of Commerce students in Rural Area is 32.72% and urban area is 30.22% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 2.5%.
4. The General Aptitude of Art students in Rural Area is 34.24% and urban area is 32.97% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 1.27%.
5. The General Aptitude Applied Art students in Rural Area are 4.54% and urban area is 5.34% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 0.80%.
6. The General Aptitude other field students in Rural Area are 4.24% and urban area is 3.81% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 0.43%.
7. The Interest of Medical field students in Rural Area is 15.45% and urban area is 17.70% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 2.25%.
8. The Interest of Engineering students in Rural Area is 16.66% and urban area is 19.08% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 2.42%.
9. The Interest of Commerce students in Rural Area is 28.48% and urban area is 24.42% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 4.06%.
10. The Interest of Art students in Rural Area is 27.12% and urban area is 24.20% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 2.92%.
11. The Interest of Fine Art students in Rural Area is 6.96% and urban area is 8.85% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 1.89%.
12. The Interest of Other field students in Rural Area is 5.30% and urban area is 6.71% of Vidarbha Region. Difference between rural and urban area is 1.41%.

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